

Detection of Anomalous Events using Smart Fusion for Smart Home Application

(Pengesanan Peristiwa Anomali Menggunakan Gabungan Penderia Untuk Aplikasi Rumah Pintar)

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ABSTRACT

A smart surveillance system is a technology that detects anomalous activities automatically. The most difficult part is to comprehend and identify both simple and abnormal activities correctly. Anomalous activities such as suspicious lingering are one of the things that need to watch out for since it can lead to unwanted events. For this study, the Complex Event Processing (CEP) method was chosen as the system expansion approach for building a Smart Surveillance System. The search-based event detector, Multi-Layered Event Detector for General Application (MEGA) was chosen to be the main subject of the system. The input of the detector contains annotated simple events from multiple proximity sensors that have been placed strategically in the selected area. The data was categorized into three noise conditions: (i) no noise (0% noise) condition, (ii) 20% noise condition and (iii) 40% noise condition. These three noise conditions depend on the location of this surveillance system whether it is used in a personal home, working area, or public area. The performance of the detector is calculated in terms of sensitivity, specificity, and average accuracy. The results obtained showed that the system gives the best performance in a no-noise condition and the least performance in the highest noise condition (40% noise). The system is also tested with four different types of noise available in the data which are (i) no noise, (ii) additional events, (iii) incomplete events, and (iv) not aligned events. It can be concluded that the higher the noise, the lower the accuracy to detect anomalous events using proximity sensors for smart home applications.

Keywords: complex event processing, smart surveillance system, anomalous activities, proximity sensors

ABSTRAK

Sistem pengawasan pintar merupakan teknologi yang berupaya untuk mengesan aktiviti anomali secara automatik. Antara bahagian yang paling mencabar adalah untuk mengesan dan memahami kedua-dua aktiviti mudah dan luar biasa dengan tepat. Pergerakan yang mencurigakan dianggap sebagai salah satu aktiviti anomali yang harus diperhatikan kerana ia boleh membawa kepada kejadian yang tidak dingini. Kaedah yang dipilih sebagai pengembangan sistem untuk membangunkan sistem pengawasan pintar dalam kajian ini adalah Pemprosesan Peristiwa Kompleks (CEP). Pengesanan peristiwa berdasarkan carian, Pengesanan Acara Berlapis untuk Aplikasi Umum (MEGA) telah dipilih untuk digunakan di dalam sistem. Data yang dicerap oleh pengesan terdiri daripada peristiwa-peristiwa mudah yang dilampirkan daripada beberapa penderia jarak yang telah ditempatkan secara strategik. Data tersebut telah dibahagikan kepada tiga jenis keadaan gangguan: (i) anotasi tiada gangguan (0% gangguan), (ii) anotasi 20% gangguan dan (iii) anotasi 40% gangguan. Ketiga-tiga keadaan ini bergantung kepada lokasi sistem pengawasan ini digunakan sama ada di rumah peribadi, kawasan pekerjaan atau kawasan awam. Prestasi pengesanan sistem ini diukur dari segi kepekaan, kekhususan dan purata ketepatan. Hasil yang diperolehi daripada kajian ini menunjukkan bahawa sistem tersebut memberikan prestasi terbaik dalam keadaan tanpa gangguan manakala prestasi yang paling sedikit di dalam keadaan gangguan tertinggi (40% gangguan). Sistem ini juga diuji dalam empat jenis situasi gangguan berbeza yang terdapat di dalam data iaitu situasi (i) tiada gangguan, (ii) peristiwa tambahan, (iii) peristiwa tidak lengkap dan (iv) peristiwa tidak sejajar. Daripada kajian ini, dapat disimpulkan bahawa semakin tinggi nilai gangguan di dalam data, semakin rendah purata ketepatan untuk mengesan kejadian anomali menggunakan penderia jarak untuk aplikasi rumah pintar.

Kata kunci: pengesan peristiwa, sistem pengawasan pintar, aktiviti anomali, penderia jarak

INTRODUCTION

The evolution of the Internet of Things (IoT) has been increasing steadily. Huge potential can be developed by combining electronics and internet facilities. Thus, giving many benefits to society. Even though Malaysia still has not yet received and optimized the new development fully, but most of the developed countries have already implemented the new idea of smart technologies. The technology of the Internet of Things (IoT) is smarter and better than the existing ones. It is also included in the Industrial Revolution 4.0 (IR 4.0) that has become a trend for automation and data exchange in technology. It also included a physical-cyber system, IoT, public computing, and cognitive computing.

As more crime and disturbance occurs, smart surveillance systems are growing in demand. The system is used to identify and describe patterns of phenomenon created by human behavior and activities or can be considered as anomalous events. As time goes longer, the area that is needed to be surveillance is getting bigger and larger. Although the system that is available nowadays such as CCTV is equipped with the basic functions required, it is still insufficient to identify every event that is occurring in the area accurately and completely. Anomalous event detection is not easy to foot. The majority of the smart surveillance system in this era implemented the use of CCTV. But, the problem occurs that solely depends on CCTV is inadequate to identify the situation where complex event processing is needed. The system requires more data and a complex software to process simple events accurately even though it is already equipped with the function to detect the complex event by itself.

Therefore, the system requires an upgrade by creating a smart surveillance system based on proximity sensors to detect the location of someone based on real-time events so that the anomaly detector will be more accurate and increasing the overall surveillance system's effectiveness.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Surveillance systems are not something new in this age or era. Back in 1942, the first surveillance system was created in Germany. Then, the United State of America (USA) starts to commercialize the application of a smart surveillance system in 1947. The importance of the surveillance system has been acknowledged by many countries as it gives a good sense of security in many ways. For many years, a great deal of studies has been done focusing on the use of this framework such as the development of home monitoring application and intelligent observation for a conventional reason (Ali, 2016; Antoniou and Angelov, 2016), screen dislodged action recognition framework (Babutain et al., 2015) and smart

monitoring framework for a secure condition from battle, uproars of brutality fights, alarm conduct and fervor (Fookes et al., 2010). But, to develop a good smart surveillance system requires a lot of time and effort. This is because making the system more effective and capable to accurately detect the events correctly is not an easy task. Several algorithms and approaches have been developed to achieve it. One of the most effective ways is the use of the Complex Event Processing (CEP) approach.

The terms Simple Events (SE) and Complex Events (CE) are used in the CEP system to express the flow of the system. CE is a combination of SE that is detected or acquired from event generators using the hardware depending on the system itself. CE is concluded from the connection of past and current simple events with the past complex event under pre-decided transient and spatial imperative. This framework at that point executes the relief activity naturally for chose occasions. CEP has risen as another worldview in taking care of this issue by playing the job as a middleware, giving noteworthy details, and enhancing the framework computerization through filtering, aggregating, and developing the complex events (Zacheilas et al., 2015). CEP has become one of the main hot topics that caught the researcher's attention in the last few decades.

A CEP framework that conveys organize hubs registering capacity to decrease traffic waste because of correspondence information for a wireless sensor network (WSN) has been presented by Li & Bingwen (2010) by authorizing local real-time event processing resulting to spare system traffic and diminish impact possibility. To help complex event processing over single distributed event stream, a superior various leveled Probabilistic CEP (PCEP) philosophy which amplifies the employments of both broadened Nondeterministic Finite Automaton (NFA) model and a tree-based query model was recommended by Wang et al. (2013). This methodology works significantly more powerful over distributed event stream with huge sliding window size, yet because of immature optimization of the query model, CEP can only be constricted for NFA based PCEP engine. To perform complex event processing in a sensor network before dispersing them to goals, Saleh & Sattler (2013) proposed the use of In-Network Distributed CEP (INDCEP). They built up a beginning phase in-arrange NFA-based complex event detection with low information transferring energy to procure information from the sensor network.

A straightforward and quick review shows that analysis while the system typically uses the specialists devised rule patterns, most specialist's center more around the CEP configuration query, event-processing language, and advancement of real-time (Mehdiyev et al., 2015). By consolidating

CEP middleware with information mining approaches; it can ad-lib the absence of Machine Learning (ML) in present exploration works (Mehdiyev et al., 2015). A few ML detectors have been actualized in domains, for example, interruption detection and fingerprint identification for intrigue event pattern identification from sensor information streams (Lee et al., 1999). Past work on

CEP based smart monitoring was likewise done by Saad (2017). The outcomes demonstrated that the methodology of CEP is extremely encouraging for the smart monitoring system. Complex event detection comprises a few activities such as the selection of monitoring area, data acquisition, event classification, complex event detection, and system effectiveness measurement.

FIGURE 1. The Block Diagram of Smart Surveillance System

METHODOLOGY

This research was done with the objective to develop an anomalous event detection system by only utilizing the proximity sensors based on the CEP approach. The monitoring area decided for this research was the CAISER Operating Room, Faculty

of Engineering & Built Environment, UKM. The 3 major steps involved in the experiment are (1) Event Classification, (2) Data Acquisition, and lastly (3) Complex Event Detection using *CA-CED*.

Event Classification

TABLE 1. Lower-level Event Classification

Class	Simple Event	Event Level	Rules of Events
1	Pluar.Gerak	0	Pluar.Gerak
2	PL1.Gerak	0	PL1.Gerak
3	PL2.Gerak	0	PL2.Gerak
4	Pdalam.Gerak	0	Pdalam.Gerak
5	Pd2.Gerak	0	Pd2.Gerak
6	Pd3.Gerak	0	Pd3.Gerak
7	Pd4.Gerak	0	Pd4.Gerak
8	Pd5.Gerak	0	Pd5.Gerak
9	Pintu.Buka	0	Pintu.Buka
10	Pintu.Tutup	0	Pintu.Tutup

TABLE 2. Higher-level Event Classification

Class	Complex Event	Event Level	Aturan Peristiwa
1	Org.KeluarBilik	1	Pdalam.Gerak > Pintu.Buka > Pluar.Gerak
2	Org.MasukBilik	1	Pluar.Gerak > Pintu.Buka > Pdalam.Gerak
3	Org.LuarBlk(IN)	1	PL1.Gerak > PL2.Gerak
4	Org.LuarBlk(OUT)	1	PL2.Gerak > PL1.Gerak
5	Org.ArahMeja	1	Pdalam.Gerak > Pd2.Gerak > Pd3.Gerak
6	Org.ArahPintu(1)	1	Pd3.Gerak > Pd2.Gerak > Pdalam.Gerak
7	Org.ArahMonitor	1	Pdalam.Gerak > Pd4.Gerak > Pd5.Gerak
8	Org.ArahPintu(2)	1	Pd5.Gerak > Pd4.Gerak > Pdalam.Gerak
9	Org.KeluarBlk(IN)	1	Pluar.Gerak > PL2.Gerak
10	Org.KeluarBlk(OUT)	1	Pluar.Gerak > PL1.Gerak
11	Pintu.Ditutup	1	Pintu.Buka > Pintu.Tutup
12	Pintu.TakDitutup	2	Pintu.Buka > BUKAN Pintu.Ditutup > BUKAN Pintu.Ditutup > BUKAN Pintu.Ditutup
13	Bilik.XDihuni	2	Org.KeluarBilik > BUKAN Org.MasukBilik > BUKAN Org.MasukBilik
14	Bilik.Dihuni	2	Org.MasukBilik > BUKAN Org.KeluarBilik > BUKAN Org.KeluarBilik
15	Jumpa.Doktor	2	Org.ArahMeja > BUKAN Org.ArahPintu > BUKAN Org.ArahPintu

Data Acquisition

FIGURE 2. The Schematic Layout of the surveillance area

Ambiguity Matrix

TABLE 3. Event detection from rule template matching process

Actual Event	Detector Result	Classification
Not Occurred	Not Detected	TN (True Negative)
Not Occurred	Detected	FP (False Positive)
Occurred	Not Detected	FN (False Negative)
Occurred	Detected	TP (True Positive)

The system effectiveness measurement is needed after the CED of the data has been completed to ensure the results of the process. There are two (2) methods used, which are Ambiguity Matrix (Table 3), and Receiver Operating Characteristic (ROC) plot. For this research, the Ambiguity Matrix is suitable to use because the system contains a lot of classification. This event consists of an actual event and predicted event that has been set up by the classification. Based on the matrix in Table 3, there are a few calculations that need to be done to measure the effectiveness of the matrix system such as:

$$True\ Positive\ Rate\ (TPR) = \frac{TP}{TP + FN} \quad (1)$$

$$False\ Positive\ Rate\ (FPR) = \frac{FP}{FP + TN} \quad (2)$$

$$Accuracy\ (TPR) = \frac{TP + TN}{TP + FN + TN + FP} \quad (3)$$

Receiver Operating Characteristic (ROC)

The second method is to use the ROC plot method, which uses the TPR or sensitivity as the Y-axis and FPR or specification for the X-axis where the points can be obtained from the ambiguity matrix above. Every value of TPR and FPR obtained from the matrix will give a point and thus will form a curve in the ROC plot. An example of the ROC plot is in Figure 4.

Figure 4 ROC curve plot

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Ambiguity Matrix Analysis

For this research, an ideal situation is created as a mimic data for the simulation. An ideal situation means that the situation created is perfect where the data that has been detected only focus on the movement of a single person and does not contain any type of noise for example misaligned noise or an unexpected movement detected from another sensor that is not supposed to be detected.

Table 4 shows the types of noise introduced for comparison in this research. There are 3 sequence files with a fluctuating degree of artificially prompted noise: set 1 with 0% noise speaking to the ideal data securing condition, set 2 with 20% noise speaking to a low commotion condition, and set 3 with 40% noise speaking to a high commotion condition.

TABLE 4. Types of noise introduced

Type of Noise	Annotated Events	Amount of noise introduced	% Noise
No noise	100	0	0.0
Low Noise	80	20	20.0
High Level of Noise	60	40	40.0

TABLE 5. Ambiguity Matrix Analysis for Anomalous

Detection System	True Positive Rate	False Positive Rate	Average Accuracy
No Noise – 0%			
	0.820	0.004	0.839
Low Noise – 20%			
MEGA	0.700	0.008	0.714
High Noise – 40%			
	0.563	0.004	0.571

Events

Table 5 shows the average accuracy of the surveillance system to detect the sequence of events while Figure 5 shows the ROC curve plot of the system in those three different types of noise conditions. Based on the research, the surveillance system has the highest value of average accuracy when there is no amount of noise introduced into the data. Meanwhile, the higher the amount of noise introduced in the data, the lower the average accuracy of the system will be. This problem occurs due to the detection system got confused from all of the incorrect sequences of events in the data when compared with the event classification rules, which results in the lower accuracy of detection of the anomalous event correctly.

FIGURE 5. ROC Curve Plot for Anomalous Events Ambiguity Matrix Analysis

Performance Parameters

To identify the performance parameters of the surveillance system, a few types of different situation data needs to be produced and simulate from the same mimic data of this simulation. Those situations are categorized into 4 different types of noise which are no noise, additive noise, losses noise, and misaligned noise. Additive noise situation means that the event data that has been detected possess some noise such as the same information is repeated continuously in a short period. Losses noise situation means that the information of the simple event detected by the system is not enough to be detected as a complex event. Once all four of the data has been run through the CED process, the results were shown in Table 6.

TABLE 6. Ambiguity Matrix Analysis for four different types of noise

Detection system	True Positive Rate	False Positive Rate	Average Accuracy
No Noise			
	0.622	0.002	0.769
Additive Noise			
	0.527	0.002	0.692
Losses Noise			
MEGA	0.400	0.001	0.462
Misaligned Noise			
	0.311	0.001	0.346

Based on the Ambiguity Matrix Analysis in Table 6, the surveillance system does not have that much of a difference when comparing the no noise situation and additive noise situation. Both of those situations resulting in an almost similar average accuracy and a good number of TPR, which are in the range of (0.50-0.65). But, for the losses noise and misaligned noise, both have a very low number of TPR and average accuracy. This shows that even though the accuracy of the system in an additive noise situation is not as high as the one in a no noise situation, it can still perform the same quality of surveillance. But for both the loss noise and misaligned noise situation, the system cannot perform as good surveillance.

This CAISER platform-based surveillance system can be used with a variety of devices. Among the studies that have been done and emphasized is to use of camera devices. As understood, device differences will give different results in terms of accuracy, sensitivity as well as true and false-positive rates. With the results of different studies, various methods can be used to improve the effectiveness of such surveillance systems. Differences between the effectiveness of surveillance systems between camera devices and distance devices.

TABLE 7. Ambiguity Matrix Analysis depends on the type of devices

Type Of Device	True Positive Rate	False Positive Rate	Average Accuracy
No Noise			
Proximity sensors	0.820	0.004	0.839
Camera	0.483	0.023	0.975
Low Noise			
Proximity sensors	0.7	0.008	0.714
Camera	0.438	0.025	0.967
High Noise			
Proximity sensors	0.563	0.004	0.571
Camera	0.428	0.020	0.974

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Based on the ambiguity matrix table above, there is a difference between the true-positive rate (TPR) and false-positive rate (FPR) for the two types of devices. The monitoring system that uses a proximity sensor has a higher true-positive rate (TPR) than a camera and has a lower false-positive rate (FPR) than cameras. However, the average accuracy of the proximity sensor is less than that of the camera. This shows that surveillance systems that use the camera as the main device have better effectiveness. Although studies for these camera devices were conducted in different areas, the analysis obtained from the study can still be used for comparison.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, a smart surveillance system based on complex event processing (CEP) using a CAISER platform with a distance sensing device has been developed and can be implemented well. This system can identify complex events at a high rate. Recognition results have high effectiveness and can achieve an average accuracy of more than 80%. A comparison of smart surveillance systems

using the CAISER platform between camera devices and proximity sensors has also been done.

This study prioritizes the smart monitoring system based on the CAISER platform. By comparing surveillance systems using camera devices and distance sensing devices, various types of advantages and disadvantages can be studied. For example, the proximity sensors cost a lot less compared with cameras thus giving more options on how to spend most of the extra budget or save it. But the camera gives a lot more information in the form of a video, unlike the proximity sensors which can only give a response when a person walks through it. To get a more effective smart surveillance system, the combination of both camera devices and distance sensors can obtain more and better data and provide higher accuracy.

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